

Massive Open Online Course
MAKING SENSE OF GENOMIC DATA: COVID-19 WEB-BASED BIOINFORMATICS

About the course

Over the past decade, sequencing technologies have become more accessible and sequencing data has increased exponentially, especially due to the COVID-19 pandemic. However, bioinformatics capacity is still limited. This course will provide concepts and tools for web-based SARS-CoV-2 analyses, aiming to mitigate the bottleneck on sequencing analyses.

Learning outcomes

- Describe the SARS-CoV-2 viral genomic structure
- Evaluate different sequence analysis outputs
- Apply a basic analytical web-based pipeline
- Examine how variant calling contributes to epidemiological inferences

Target audience

This course is designed for diagnostic and healthcare professionals, researchers, and anyone involved in the testing and analysis of disease samples. It will also be advantageous to researchers specialising in web-based bioinformatics, diagnostics, diseases, or pandemics.

Material repository website

https://wcscourses.github.io/COG-Train_Resources/making_sense_home.html

Content

Week 1 - Introduction to viral genomics

Glossary

Frequently asked questions

SARS-CoV-2 replication cycle

SARS-CoV-2 genomic landscape

Overview of genomic, sub-genomic and anti-genomic sequences

Introduction to sequencing methods

How is SARS-CoV-2 sequencing done?

Amplicon-based sequencing

Overview of different data formats

What is bioinformatics?

Overview of web-based bioinformatics analyses using Galaxy

Importing data onto Galaxy

Processing data on Galaxy

Building a workflow on Galaxy

Using existing workflows on Galaxy

Week 2 - Exploring the pipelines available

Garbage in/Garbage out: importance of generating good data and cleaning up

Data cleaning and quality control

FastQC and MultiQC tools

Assess quality with FastQC

Assembly of SARS-CoV-2 genome and sequence alignment

Assembly tutorial

Variant calling and annotation

Variant calling tutorial

Using and interpreting Nextclade

Signatures of co-infection, recombination and contamination

What are clades, lineages and variants?

Prediction of minor variants and drug resistance

Identification of recombinants

Introduction to phylogenetics: tools and models

Transmission detection: travel-associated, hospital and community transmission

Tutorial on phylogenetics

Quality control in phylogenetics

Week 3 - Introduction to genomic epidemiology of COVID-19

The importance of sample and data consent

Ethics in data sharing

Metadata: standardisation and collection tools

Ownership of analyses tools and pipelines

Best practices for data sharing

Data quality metrics

Pros and cons of public databases for data sharing

When and why to obtain sequencing data

How and where to obtain the public data

Challenges and limitations of data sharing
Best practices for presenting your data
Public health reports and sharing
Resources

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